

High Density Study of Vaporiser before Mansoon Weather for Density Dependent Parameter

Paper Id : 18233 Submission Date : 15/09/2023 Acceptance Date : 21/09/2023 Publication Date : 25/09/2023

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10113093

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Lakshman Sharan Singh

Assistant Professor
Physics
M P College
Mohania, Bihar, India

Abstract

Aerosol characteristics over Mohania region during premonsoon (March - May) period were analyzed for year 2016. Aerosol optical properties and angstrom exponent were measured using MICROTUPS-II Sunphotometer. The mean AOD for the period of study was found to be 0.78 where as mean angstrom exponent (AE at 440 - 870 nm) was found to be 0.30. Average concentrations of PM_{2.4} was found to be 124.10 µg/m³ respectively, which clearly demonstrates dominance of coarse mode particles particularly in this season.

Keywords High Density Study of Vaporiser, Mansoon, Weather, Density, Dependent, Parameter.

Introduction

Atmospheric aerosols play an important role in earth's radiation budget and which further causes implications to regional climate [1, 2]. Assessment of effect of aerosols on climate requires not only the knowledge of its regional and global distribution but its various properties [3]. Thus it becomes important to improve aerosol characterization on regional basis with high spatial and temporal resolutions.

Aim of study The study has been carried out using MICROTUPS II Sunphotometer and two High volume samplers (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. during March to May 2016 over Mohania.

Review of Literature The Indo-Gangetic basin (IGB) is one of the highly populated regions in the world, where high concentration of population live and are exposed to enormous pollution produced by various natural and anthropogenic sources [4, 5]. This region experiences emissions of various anthropogenic and natural aerosols throughout the year [6]. Moreover, during pre-monsoon or summer seasons, IGB receives heavier loads of natural dust aerosols, transported from the neighboring Desert regions (Thar Desert) of western Rajasthan in India [7].

Analysis

The study site Mohania represents (25°28' N and 82°97' E; 82.2 m AMSL) an urban environmental location over central part of IGB characterized by multiple sources of aerosol loading throughout the year. The present study involves MICROTUPS-II Sunphotometer manufactured by Sun light company limited USA and two high volume samplers manufactured by Envirotech private ltd., India. The MICROTUPS-II sun-photometer is a portable hand held sun-photometer for direct solar irradiance measurement in different wavelengths of 440, 500, 675, 870 and 936 nm. The hourly data of Aerosol Optical Thickness at 500 nm had been taken during the period of study over Varanasi at our Department of Physics, Institute of Science, Banaras Hindu University, India. The high volume samplers were deployed at terrace of the Department at height of approximately 8 feet.

Result and Discussion

Aerosol optical depth and angstrom exponent are two very important parameters to study aerosol properties which are analogous to Angstrom power law and related to each other by expression given as $\tau_\lambda = \beta\lambda^{-\alpha}$ where, τ_λ , is AOD at the wavelength λ , β is the turbidity coefficient which is equal to AOD at $\lambda = 1\mu\text{m}$ and α is the AE. Enhanced AOD was observed during the month of April, May and June of the particular which is shown in Figure 1. Average AOD for the entire period of study was found to be 0.78.

Variation of AE represents that there are different types of aerosols present over the region during the measurement period of pre-monsoon season, which may be due to day-to-day variability in weather conditions and emission factors. During pre-monsoon season, enhancement in AOD is attributed to aerosol loading due to dust-storm events coming from far source region, Arabian Peninsula and African regions. There is an increasing trend in AOD from April to June at the Authorized licensed use limited to: University of Exeter. Downloaded on June 20,2020 at 20:46:34 UTC from IEEE Xplore. Restrictions apply. location during pre- monsoon, which may be due to dust storm and anthropogenic aerosol sources [4] depicts variation in concentrations of particulate matter of both types over the Varanasi. Figure 1. Variation of AOD during the month of April, May and June 2017.